

Additional File 4. MSOT images of GNR-labelled macrophages in different organs. Snapshot images of the abdomen of mice, showing the (a) liver, delineated with red lines and (b) kidney, delineated with a yellow line or spleen, delineated with a green line. Images correspond to baseline imaging (pre-administration) and 4h post IV administration of GNR-labelled RAW macrophages. GNR-labelling generates MSOT contrast, seen as an increase in pixel brightness for areas corresponding to liver and spleen. Kinetic imaging over a period of 4h was used to generate data shown in Fig. 1f. (c) Quantification of the MSOT mean pixel intensity in the liver, spleen or kidneys 4h post administration of GNR-labelled RAW macrophages IV or IC. Data is displayed as fold changes in pixel intensity in respect to baseline measurements.